

THE CRIME DETECTION SYSTEM FOR WOMEN

Dr. S. S. Sreeja Mole*, **Dr. K. Sujatha****, **D. Devi Kala Rathinam*****,
A. Santhiya Grace*** & **M. K. Bhuvana*****

* Professor & Head, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Christu Jyoti Institute of Technology & Science, Jangaon, Telangana

** Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Sri Krishna College of Engineering and Technology, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

*** M.E Student, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Sri Krishna College of Engineering and Technology, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. S. S. Sreeja Mole, Dr. K. Sujatha, D. Devi Kala Rathinam, A. Santhiya Grace & M. K. Bhuvana, "The Crime Detection System for Women", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 39-43, 2018.

Abstract:

India is most traditional country throughout the world. In India they give more respect for the women. Nowadays there are many crimes occur in our major cities like Delhi, Mumbai etc. In India, for every one hour 26 crimes occurs against women and recent survey says that for every two minutes the occurrence of crime is one. In last decades the women's are uneducated and they completely depend on men's. But now days the women's are educated and there are travelling throughout the world. Our government proposed the act Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961. Using this act the dowry has been reduced. Our government has proposed many acts to avoid the crime rate against women. In India the working men is 65% and working women is 52%. In 2011 the working women is 14.7% and men is 54.3%. Women are working mainly in IT sectors in India as well as in overseas. The growth of women as well as the crime against the women has been increased in society. In India Andhra Pradesh has the highest crime against women. Now the current Prime Minister Mr. Modi started digital India for women empowerment. Women are developed in multiple sectors and also they play major role in government sectors. Women are affected by many crimes like kidnapping, abduction and rape. In 2020, Women will become more superpower.

Introduction:

India is 2nd largest country in population. In that Woman occupies half of the population in India. In India many crimes occur against the women but it is projected mainly in Nirbhaya's incident. This incident happens in 16th December, 2012. There are many crimes like rape, acid attack and many more crimes are happening in India. Not only had the crime rate stopped in Nirbhaya's incident the crime rate has been increasing rapidly. The National Crime Records Bureau of India reported for every three minute the crime takes place. The crime done by husband and relatives are punished under the section 498-A of Indian Penal Code (IPC). The Kidnapping is the major crime happen against women (315,074), next major crime against the women is rape (243,051), with (104,151) the insult to modesty of women plays the major role and finally crime is dowry death (80,833). Due do these crimes women's committee suicide (3,734). The women are protected from domestic violence under the act of 426. Women plays major role in developing the society. Majority Of the women are working in different sectors. In India 1.4 million women are working as panchayat leaders. The women are working in agriculture, construction etc. women are educated than men. Nowadays women are working as men in the entire field. Only due to these crimes the women are affected. Mr. Modi government started protecting the women from crimes. Education plays major role in developing the women. Women are equal to men but they are affected only by men. For protecting the women from rape, dowry, kidnapping our government has proposed many acts to protect the women from crime.

Year	Rape	Molestation	Kidnapping	Bad Behaviour
2012	198	515	137	183
2013	394	1161	251	444
2014	610	1616	309	364
2015	710	2008	944	412
2016	712	2180	1172	425
2017	78	364	203	20

The crime rate against the women in the year 2007 is 0.13. During 2007 the crime rate against the women is very low. Day by day the crime rate is increasing. In 2008 the crime rate against the women is 0.89. In 2009 the crime rate against the women is 1.58. Compare to 2007 the crime rate is increasing gradually. In 2011 the crime rate against the women is 2.09. In 2011 the crime rate against the women is 2.57. In 2012 the crime rate against the women is 2.64. Crime rate between the years 2011 to 2012 is 0.7. The rate is controlled while comparing to 2007 to 2010. The crime rate in the year 2013 is 3.38. The crime rate in the year 2014 is 5.99. The crime rate has been increased suddenly in 2014. The crime rate in the year 2015 is 5.14. Compare to 2014 the crime rate is decreased. The crime rate in the year 2016 is 6.83. Again the crime rate has been increased. The crime rate in the year 2017 is 7.41. From past few years 2017 has the highest crime rate.

Literature Survey:

Aarti Bansal proposed the Performance Comparison of Data Mining Techniques to Analyze Crime against Women [1]

In this paper the data mining is used for protecting the women from crime. To handle large amount of data the data mining is used. Using data mining only needed information can be extracted. The data mining can be used in medical, income tax department, engineering, banking sectors etc. The following are the steps used in data mining. They are

- ✓ The raw data are extraction from repositories.
- ✓ After extraction it is loaded into data mining database.
- ✓ The data from the database are transformed into the table.
- ✓ Pattern discovery can be done by clustering, regression and classification algorithm.
- ✓ Finally the data is visualized and the interpretation of result can be done.

In this paper the following three algorithms are used. They are

- ✓ Decision Tree
- ✓ Apriori
- ✓ K-Nearest Neighbor

The Crime against women takes place not only in India but also throughout the world. It is necessary to find the certain age group people involving in crime. Then to identify the certain age group of girls are victim. This information can be gathered by analyzing the old crime cases. Using the old crime cases we can also identify the major areas where the crime takes place. With the help of this information the government, police and society people can create the peaceful society. When this information is known to her, the women can protected from crime by her own. The above algorithms are called as data classification algorithm. It is used to analyzes crime happens against the women.

Prof. Sankalp Mehta, Sachin Janawade, Vinayak Kittur, Suraj Munnole, Sandhya Basannavar proposed An Android Based Application for Women Security [2]

This paper is completely based on android mobiles. This application is mainly based on Global Positioning System (GPS). Using this application we can send the alert message to the nearby contacts. On the emergency situation if you want to get help from nearby contacts. This application not only sends the alert

message but also it send the alert sound. These alert message and sound can be sending while shaking the mobile phone of victim. It also send alert message to nearby police station. With the help of GPS the location of victim can be found.

This application can be implemented in 3 different types of application module. They are

- ✓ Victim app module
- ✓ Guardian app module
- ✓ Server module

Victim App Module:

There are few steps for using this Victim app module

- ✓ In the android mobile this application should be installed.
- ✓ Open the application and enter the user ID, name and phone number
- ✓ Click the ok button. The registration can be done successfully.
- ✓ The given mobile number is already registered. It shows, the given mobile number is already registered.

Guardian App Module:

There are few steps for using this Guardian app module

- ✓ In the android mobile this application should be installed.
- ✓ Add the phone number of Guardian and click the register button.
- ✓ The registration can be done successfully.
- ✓ The given mobile number is already registered. It shows, the given mobile number is already registered.

Server Module:

There are few steps for using this Server app module

- ✓ After installing the above two application two tables are created in server application
- ✓ The one table is victim table and another one is guardian table.
- ✓ There are five columns in victim table. The columns contain victim ID, victim NAME, victim PHONE-NUMBER, victim LATITUDE and LONGITUDE.
- ✓ There are three columns in Guardian table. The columns contain Guardian PHONE-NUMBER, Guardian LATITUDE and LONGITUDE.

Sainath B Gadhe, Ganesh Chinchansure, Amar Kumar, Mritunjay Ojha proposed the Women Anti-Rape Belt [3]. It helps the women at many difficult situations. It is a location tracker which trackers the location of the victim. Using these application women can send alert message by manual or automatic setting. In this android application the flow of electricity with normal AA sized with the 9 volts battery is connected. Using the GPS the alert message can be send to predefined contacts. This application is suitable for smart phones. The smart phones must have the android version of at least 2.3 which is Gingerbread. The mobile phone is connected to Arduino. The connectivity can be done using Bluetooth. The alert message will send to predefined contacts when the key is pressed. This application can be open only by entering the password. If the victim is unable to press the key due to some reason the arduino will monitor and send the message. The alert message also sends to nearby police station.

Proposed System:

While long pressing the up arrow of the volume button it sends the location of the user automatically to the intended people based on manual setting of time interval for location based messages and also to all the nearby registered contacts. It broadcasts the emergency messages to the contacts based on the current location of the user. While long pressing the down arrow of the volume button it gives the alert sound as Police siren. In existing application they use many alert sounds like whistle, girls sound but only in this application the Police siren is used. It helps the user to get immediate help from the society. This application contain emergency numbers like women welfare, blood bank etc. It helps the user not to memorize all those numbers. A self-defense technique makes them self dependable as well as make the society to come forward for help. It sends the alert message to all the registered contacts and default to parents. In this application the GPS can be ON automatically. It avoids the situations when one forgets to turn on it.

Conclusion:

This project focuses on providing security to users which includes location-based services, SMS services, GPS services and system Architecture. Throughout the development of the first phase of the project, we have learned much more new skills ranging from vital experience in working as a team and the new technologies. The application eliminates the manual communication difficulties currently faced by the user. It is developed in a user-friendly manner since the application is developed using Android. The application is very fast and any transaction can be process across the network.

References:

1. Bansal, A. Performance Comparison of Data Mining Techniques to Analyse Crime against Women.
2. Hopkins, C., & Mc Keown, R. (2002). Education for sustainable development: an international perspective. Education and sustainability: Responding to the global challenge, 13.
3. Rahman, A. (1999). Micro-credit initiatives for equitable and sustainable development: Who pays?. World development, 27(1), 67-82.

4. Lawson, H. A. (2005). Empowering people, facilitating community development, and contributing to sustainable development: The social work of sport, exercise, and physical education programs. *Sport, Education and Society*, 10(1), 135-160.
5. Pavlova, M. (2008). *Technology and vocational education for sustainable development: Empowering individuals for the future (Vol. 10)*. Springer Science & Business Media.
6. Braidotti, R. (1994). *Women, the environment and sustainable development: towards a theoretical synthesis*. Zed Books.
7. Mihelcic, J. R., Phillips, L. D., & Watkins Jr, D. W. (2006). Integrating a global perspective into education and research: Engineering international sustainable development. *Environmental Engineering Science*, 23(3), 426-438.
8. Mayoux, L. (2001). Tackling the down side: Social capital, women's empowerment and micro-finance in Cameroon. *Development and change*, 32(3), 435-464.
9. World Health Organization. (2005). *Addressing violence against women and achieving the Millennium Development Goals*.
10. Ugbomeh, G. M. (2001). Empowering women in agricultural education for sustainable rural development. *Community Development Journal*, 36(4).